

Research Article

The CSR Activities for the Quality Control and Sustainable Development

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A B S T R A C T

Today, the responsibility to act legally and morally in the pursuit of profit is the notion of social responsibility, typically which is called "corporate social responsibility" (CSR). The sustainability approach towards CSR is premised on the idea that a company must remain economically viable in the long-term, for the viability the company must take into consideration for other stakeholders beyond the shareholders. In the 1970s, corporate social responsibility efforts, quality control and sustainable development were first brought to light. They have remained inseparable up till the present day. The following research paper explores how the existence of CSR activities offer possibilities and assist business organizations to depict their company and build a better image of themselves to the society and stakeholders. The focus of the article is on the social and economic elements of the business environment. The organizations no longer have the luxury of choosing whether or not to commit to CSR efforts. Both the organizations and the people of the society stand to benefit from this circumstance, making it a win-win scenario for everyone involved. As businesses, they have the opportunity to demonstrate their fundamental beliefs, provide advantages to customers, live up to the responsibility they have to contribute to the expansion of the nation's economic development.

Keywords: Origins, Evolution Quality Control, Sustainable Development, Corporate Social Responsibility, CSR

Introduction

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is a concept whereby organizations consider the interests of society by taking responsibility for the impact of their activities on customer, suppliers, employees, shareholders, communities, other stakeholders, as well as the environment. There are other terms like socially responsible investment, corporate citizenship, philanthropy for CSR. The term "sustainability" also has emerged, along with social responsibility and corporate governance, as important subject matters for

business today. Mishra 2020 assessed budgetary constraint using theory of constrain in road project. Even review based analysis conducted by Mishra, 2018: Mishra and Magar, 2017 and Mishra and Aithal, 2022 identify budget is an issue for infrastructure development projects which is also supported by Mishra and Aithal, 2021 by highlighting the gap in budget in absence of foreign aids. So, Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) may be an option for overcoming the issue. Every major detailed content and argument about CSR began to take form in the mid and late 20th century, i.e., during the 1950s. But practices related to social upliftment

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had started in the mid to late 1800s. The first traces of improving employee productivity and philanthropy can be found during this time when there emerged an industrial betterment movement in Great Britain and America. In the early 1900s period which was termed as the 'trusteeship management', corporate managers took responsibility to create a balance between maximizing wealth and claims from customers, employees, society. Sophie Muirhead has considered this period as the 'prelegalization period' of corporate contributions playing a central role in the development of modern CSR. Patrick Murphy, writing in the University of Michigan Business Review in 1978, established four eras of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), the first of which supported the phase that occurred before and after the 1950s. According to him, the time duration that lasted up to the 1950s was referred to as the "Philanthropic era." During this time period, various organizations' contributions to charitable causes received far more attention than any other topic. The years 1953-1967 were collectively referred to as the "Awareness era" since this was the time duration during which businesses began to become more conscious of their responsibilities toward the company and the society to which it belonged.

From 1968 to 1973, a duration that has come to be known as the "Issue era," businesses started becoming involved in many problems that revolved around prejudice of race, pollution, other related topics. The "Responsive era," which lasted from 1974 to 1978, was the period when businesses first began to take corporate social responsibility operations seriously. The explication provided by Murphy is helpful, it is congruent with our deliberation both at this time and in the future. Prior to the inception of the acronym CSR, the concept of Corporate Social Responsibility was referred to simply as social responsibility. The explanation of Murphy is helpful to us at this time, it will continue to be useful and consistent with our deliberation in the future. Before it was rebranded as CSR, social responsibility was known as corporate social responsibility. Carroll contended that Howard Bowen should be recognized as the "Father of Corporate Social Responsibility." In the 1950s, there were three notions presented: the concept of corporate managers acting in the role of public trustees; the concept of balancing conflicting claims to corporate sources; and the concept of appreciating philanthropy as an expression of corporate interest for charitable purposes.

Literature Review

Corporate Social Responsibility is referred to as "corporate citizenship" and can involve incurring short-term costs that do not provide an immediate financial benefit to the company, but instead promote positive social and environmental change (Investopedia). The first publication of Post 1950s era, 'Social Responsibilities of

the Businessman' by Howard R. Bowen in 1953 is considered to be the beginning of this period. He described social responsibilities of businessmen as 'their obligations to pursue those policies, to make those decisions, or to follow those lines of action which are desirable in terms of the objectives and values of our society'. Literature on CSR expanded in 1960's and 1970's.

William C. Fredrick was an early pioneer of CSR and one of its many supporters. During the 1960s, Clarence C. Walton was an influential figure in the community and was known for his insightful ideas. Even in the 1960s, charity remained the most apparent form of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).

In the 1970s, one of the most influential authors on the subject of corporate social responsibility was George Steiner. In the 1980s, there were a variety of approaches that might be used to define CSR activities. The year 1987 marked the beginning of the adoption of several new principles of sustainable development, which continued throughout the 1990s.

There were debates over how to approach the problem, which we now refer to as "sustainable development," more than a century before the word "sustainable development" came into usage.

The period from 2001 to 2002 was guided not by CSR principles but rather by observational research. On the intellectual front, Schwartz and Carroll have further provided an approach to corporate social responsibility that is based on a three-domain framework. In the three-domain approach, Carroll's four CSR categories were reduced to just three: economic, legal, ethical considerations.

The authors of the book "Doing the Most Good for Your Company and Your Cause," Philips Kotler and Nancy Lee, discussed the 25 best practices that may serve as a roadmap for companies' Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) initiatives. There are six primary classes of social reasons that may be applied to the practices:

- Cause promotion, which raises people's awareness of and concern for various social concerns
- Marketing that is tied to a charitable cause
- Corporate Social Marketing
- Corporate Philanthropy
- Participating in community service
- Engaging in practices that are responsible to the business.

CSR has been a widespread phenomenon during the course of the previous 20 years, but notably in the 2000s. The 20th century was characterized by a variability of views on human development, both good and bad. People's conceptions of how development and expansion should occur shifted as a direct result of the technical and economic

shifts that took place during this time period, when the environmental crisis was also at its worst. At this period, the use of newly developed technology, the production of fossil fuels and oil, growing levels of environmental concern were all on the rise on a global scale. The 21st century has focused on implementation of CSR initiatives. This attention not only by businesses but governments likewise is a direct impact of recent corporate failures like the Enron, Union Carbide and the collapse of giants like Arthur Anderson etc.

The United Nations World Commission on Environment and Development came up with the idea that development is okay, but the primary emphasis should be on sustainable development.

The Business sustainability continuum illustrates that the continual success and “sustainability” of the business can only be achieved by an adherence to four core values: Economic, indicating that a business obviously must have a viable business model which fulfills a need and enables the business to make a profit; Legal, indicating that this profit must be achieved in legal manner by aligning the conduct of the business with all applicable local, national, international law; Ethical, indicating that since there may be no law or “gaps” in the law, nonetheless the business must act in a moral manner and also must act in conformity with its values, promises, obligations; and Social Responsibility, indicating that the business must focus on the community and engage in civic, philanthropic, charitable endeavors as part of the business’ overall strategic plan (Mujtaba and Cavico, 2013). Both sustainability and corporate social responsibility have their own distinct aspects, but they are also intertwined. The objective of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is to increase consumers’ faith in a company’s brand by making the organization seem responsible and by tackling pressing social problems. Sustainable development is interlinked with the normative concept of sustainability. UNESCO formulated a distinction between the two concepts as follows: “Sustainability is often thought of as a long-term goal (i.e., a more sustainable world), while sustainable development refers to the many processes and pathways to achieve it.” The concept of sustainability refers to taking actions that will have an effect on the long run and assures a healthy planet (by encouraging the production of a large amount of food), safe communities, strong economies for future generations. Sustainable development was first institutionalized with the Rio Process initiated at the 1992 Earth Summit in Rio de Janeiro in 2015 the United nation General assembly adopted the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (2015 to 2030) and explained how the goals are integrated and indivisible to achieve sustainable development at the global level (Purvis, Ben; Mao, Yong; Robinson, Darren, 2019). They address the global challenges, including poverty, inequality, climate change, environmental degradation, peace, justice.

Objective of the Study

- To re-discover the roots of corporate social responsibility initiatives and the beginnings of the concept of quality control and sustainable development
- To investigate how it has developed throughout the years in an environment that is always changing

Research Methodology

This is a conceptual paper that relies heavily on secondary sources of data; the method is known as a technique for doing research that involves observing the information that is already known about a certain subject.

Finding and Discussion

The actions and initiatives that are now known as CSR may trace their roots back to the concept of corporate philanthropy. Strategic CSR is philanthropic CSR that is used as a PR tool to enhance the image of the corporation. Altruistic or benevolent CSR is what is regarded an aspiration in doing good for mankind regardless of its impact on the bottom line. Altruistic or benevolent CSR is legitimate since it strives to satisfy the financial obligations of the company. Andrew Carnegie, a wealthy financier and philanthropist, was guided by his faith in the Gospel of causes in his charitable giving. In the late 1800s, John D. Rockefeller, similarly swayed by Carnegie’s example, followed suit by donating enormous quantities of money to various social organizations.

Frederick Goff, a well-known banker in Cleveland, was the person who established the Cleveland Foundation in 1914. The Cleveland Foundation is a trustee of the Cleveland Trust Corporation. Its purpose was to give the community more authority by soliciting contributions from several contributors rather than a single wealthy benefactor so that the contributors may collectively evaluate the community’s requirements and provide a response. This was the primary support structure for societies. However, it wasn’t until the 1940s that businesses were given the ability to assist charitable organizations on their own, independent of their owners or shareholders.

More than two hundred years ago, people started asking concerns about the impact that the development of our civilization would have on the environment and prosperity of our world. Thomas Robert Malthus (1766-1834) was a demographer, political theorist, country preacher in England. He is best known for writing *An Essay on the Theory of Population*, which was published in 1798. Because the rate of population expansion was too fast for the rate at which food could be produced, he predicted that eventually all of the people on the earth would perish from starvation, or at the very least, live at a level of subsistence that was inadequate. He thought that “misery, vice and

spiritual restraint” were what held society together and prevented it from falling apart.

When Carlowitz published the first book on forest sciences in 1713, he gave birth to the concept that would later be known as “sustainable development” He stated that dwindling resources offered as a signal of humanity having to preserve our resources, which he said would be as vital as our daily bread. Malthus wrote that “population, when unchecked, increased in a geometrical ratio and subsistence for man in an arithmetical ratio.”

Efficacious Factors (Positive Factors)

- Having a corporate social responsibility (CSR) strategy not only makes a sustainability more financially viable and valuable, but it also makes a company more responsible to its firms and more transparent to the general public
- Consumers are drawn to corporate firms because of their well-established reputations as responsible members of their communities
- The rise in sales motivates both large and small businesses to educate their customers about the notion of corporate social responsibility and to integrate it into their day-to-day operations

Derogatory Factors (Negative Factors)

- Even for large businesses, the cost of corporate social responsibility may be prohibitively expensive. If a company’s CEO chooses to put social causes ahead of profits, he or she should anticipate being fired and having their position filled by a target more focused on maximizing financial gain
- Green washing is a concept that refers to corporate actions that tend to be environmentally friendly but do not necessarily indicate a change in the method in which a business conducts its business It may be a good source of green financing (Mishra and Aithal, 2022)

A crucial Aspect of Business

Griffin and Mahon (1997) discovered that recognition is dependent on its surrounding environment, that the cumulative credibility is strongly linked to a company’s well-known commitment to corporate and environmental responsibility. In an economic or theoretical framework, Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is a critical predictor that helps boost credibility. The role that CSR may play in establishing a prominent position within this framework is limited to that role alone.

In addition to this, CSR may be used as a marketing technique in two primary ways (Mohr et al., 2001). Although the first strategy focuses on CSR in conjunction with the institution’s many stakeholders, the second method is centered on the idea of social marketing (Kotler, 2008).

Although the two groups have different perspectives on CSR compared to one another, they share the same point of view about the goals of a socially responsible firm that extend beyond short-term profitability.

The effect that CSR has as a method of partnership marketing, particularly in regard to the ethical and environmental aspects it encompasses. The debate between Friedman (1970) and CSR focuses primarily on three important areas: political power, managerial expertise, industrial understanding. Concerning the issue of jurisdiction, he claimed that the main responsibility of governments is to impose taxes and invest tax revenues. He said this in reference to the tasks that governments have. ‘ There is a strong appearance of a connection between the topic of politics and the choice of investors to participate or not participate.

CSR should be engaged in instead of a bigger philosophical dispute about a conflict in a corporate social system or the invisible hand that contributes to the pursuit of human wants inside the social framework. Because CSR is not a uniform model, each of the metrics will have a unique effect on the credibility of the organization when it is broken into qualitative subfields. (The behavior of the CSR is not consistent across all of the qualitative areas into which it was broken.) The characteristics of group interactions and staff diversity were not applicable in any of the specifications, but product problems and employee relationships were.) The relationship between a company’s credibility and their level of social responsibility is profoundly impacted by the nature of their social success and the industry in which they operate.

Insinuating that the businesses shouldn’t do anything that may hurt the organization’s standing in the community. The term “corporate social responsibility” (CSR) may have a number of different meanings and meanings depending on who you ask in the local business community. Some people refer to CSR as the triple bottom line, which is comprised of economic, environmental, social outcomes. Others regard CSR as corporate responsibility, corporate citizenship, corporate philanthropy, development of the society. In a nutshell, corporate social responsibility (CSR) is defined by academics as the manner in which businesses fulfill their social responsibility to all employees and to society as a whole. Examples of CSR include monetary donations, gifts to charitable activities, compliance with social regulations and criteria.

Conclusion

It has been discovered that the rising position of CSR, which covers topics such as employee wellness, environmental challenges, corporate sustainability, has a multidimensional nature. The concept of corporate social responsibility (CSR)

compels corporations to demonstrate accountability to a responsible range of stakeholders, including consumers, clients, investors. It offers a variety of programs, such as removing hazardous waste, giving to charitable organizations, providing customers with products and services, supplying consumers with goods and services, treating their employees in an ethical manner.

And despite the fact that the idea of sustainable growth has been around for more than two centuries, the widespread perception of the need to address the problems of the Industrial Age in all spheres of society, from homes to boardrooms, continues to be the most significant obstacle to sustainable development. These problems include limitless human and environmental abuse.

Implementing corporate social responsibility policies has significant impact on a company's ability to achieve sustainable growth. This is an important business practice. Contributions may be made by corporations through encouraging social responsibility from an economic viewpoint that considers the needs of the market. CSR has an upbeat future in the global business arena. The pressures of global competition will continue to intensify however, this will dictate that the 'business case' for CSR will always be at the center of attention.

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